

Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III) with Isonitrosomalondianilide

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BECAUSE of the commercial importance of ruthenium, numerous reagents have been proposed for its spectrophotometric determination¹. In the present work, isonitrosomalondianilide (HIMDA) was used as a complexing reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III). HIMDA reacts with ruthenium in hot aqueous solution to give red precipitate.

Experimental

All absorbance measurements were carried out on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. A digital Elico LI-120 pH-meter was employed for pH measurements. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson and Matthey) was dissolved in dilute HCl and the solution was standardised². HIMDA was synthesised as reported earlier³. A fresh reagent solution was prepared in 50% alcohol.

Procedure: To a suitable aliquot containing 4–50 μg of ruthenium was added a 0.1% of the reagent solution (2 ml), followed by acetate buffer (pH 6.0; 2 ml). Solution was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and heated on a water-bath for nearly 30 min and the resulting Ru(III)-HIMDA complex was extracted with chloroform (10 ml), equilibrating the mixture for 2 min. Organic phase was separated and the absorbance was measured at 410 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance spectra of 5 ppm of ruthenium complex and the reagent in chloroform solution were recorded separately. The complex shows an absorption maximum at 410 nm, whereas the absorption of the reagent being negligible. The reaction of ruthenium(III) with HIMDA is slow at room temperature. A 30 min heating on a boiling water-bath is necessary for complete colour development. After complexation, the extraction of Ru-HIMDA complex into chloroform was very fast and no

change was observed in the absorbance when the shaking time was varied from 2 to 5 min. After adjusting the desired pH of the solution (containing metal : ligand ratio of 1 : 40) from 1 to 12, they were heated for 1 h and the complex formed in each solution was extracted according the developed procedure. A constant absorbance in the pH range 5–6.5 is observed. Therefore all other studies were carried out at pH 6.0.

Beer's law was studied for 4 to 50 μg of ruthenium at 40-fold excess of reagent and extracting the complex into 10 ml of chloroform. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity values were found to be 0.01 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 10 107 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

The nature of the complex studied by Job's continuous variation method and also by the mole-ratio method was found to be 1 : 1. The composition was also determined by elemental analysis of the complex (Found : Ru, 27.45 ; C, 49.10 ; H, 3.48 ; N, 11.45 ; O, 8.47. Calcd. for : Ru, 27.52 ; C, 49.04 ; H, 3.29 ; N, 11.43 ; O, 8.71%).

The extent of interference by the other platinum metals by common ions was determined. EDTA, thiosulphate, thiourea, nitrate, Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pt^{IV} and V^{V} interfere. The interferences of Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} were eliminated by using thiosulphate and ascorbic acid respectively as a masking agents.

References

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